

**THEORETICAL ANALYSIS OF THE FORMATION AND DEVELOPMENT OF
CONCENTRATED LEARNING SKILLS IN STUDENTS**

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Kalit soʻzlar: konsentrlangan oʻquv koʻnikmalar, boshqaruv, tadqiqotchilik, konsentrizm, universal oʻquv koʻnikmalar, motivasion, texnologik.

Ключевые слова: концентрированные учебные умения, менеджмент, исследования, концентризм, универсальные учебные умения, мотивационные, технологические.

Keywords: concentrated learning skills, management, research, concentrism, universal learning skills, motivational, technological.

Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada konsentrlangan oʻquv koʻnikmalarini oʻquvchilarda shakllantirilishi va rivojlantirilishining nazariy tahlili, bu jarayonda boshqarish nazariyasi va amaliyotining ahamiyati, maktab taʼlimida oʻquvchilarda konsentrlangan oʻquv koʻnikmalarini rivojlantirishning mantiqiy sxemasi, oʻquv koʻnikmalarini rivojlantirish uchun bir qator talablari koʻrsatilgan.

Аннотация: В данной статье представлен теоретический анализ формирования и развития у учащихся навыков концентрированного обучения, значение теории и практики управления в этом процессе, логическая схема развития у учащихся навыков концентрированного обучения в школьном образовании, ряд требований к развитию навыков концентрированного обучения.

Annotation: this article shows a theoretical analysis of the formation and development of concentrated learning skills in students, the importance of management theory and practice in the process, a logical scheme for the development of concentrated learning skills in students in school education, a number of requirements for the development of learning skills.

The problem of developing educational skills in students in the world is one of the most relevant areas in the science and practice of pedagogy. The development of educational skills will be effective if the subjects of study are acquired at the creative level, in the process of solving non-traditional educational tasks and life problems. In educational institutions, it is provided through the resources of research and project activities, creating opportunities accessible to students. These resources, on the one hand, create situations for the application of general learning skills, and on the other hand, help to strengthen these skills in the practical activities of students. Theoretical and practical foundations of management are important in the development of concentrated learning skills of schoolchildren.

Management, as a continuous sequence of actions of the initiating subject, assumes the following: modeling and changing the personality of the initiating object; defining the maxad and tasks in collaborative activities; anicizing methods of achieving them; distribution of obligations among participants in management activities; establishing time limits and responsibility in the sphere of assigned activities; uniting and coordinating the actions of all participants [225-227].

Source analysis and management in the works of Bashkir researchers gave the opportunity to consider in detail various approaches to the content and implementation of periodization.

The process of developing concentrated learning skills of schoolchildren also plays an important role in the general development of the educational system of our country. Improvements to the general education system have been underway in recent years. Conceptual foundations and regulatory area, district, city, and intra-school support of the programs have been developed to promote universal educational activities (general concentrated skills) of schoolchildren.

At present, educational technologies and techniques are being developed and implemented to help improve the quality of education, including the formation and development of concentrated learning skills in students is also ignored.

The implemented structural analysis of the requirements of state educational standards has found that concepts similar to meanings such as formation and development are among the most used .

In this regard, in school education, the logical scheme for the development of concentrated learning skills in students develops as follows: in elementary school, concentrated learning skills are formed (as the basis of educational abilities) in research activities (as a basis for studying the phenomena of the surrounding world using research methods; in the main school, the development of concentrated learning skills is carried out(as the basis of educational cooperation-the ability to learn in interaction and communication), in the secondary school, the development of concentrated learning skills acquires a new quality, in which General concentrated learning skills are a means of personal development, helping to act and make decisions in difficult situations.

At the same time, a number of requirements for the development of concentrated learning skills of schoolchildren compiled by educators-Methodists are revealed, which:

- general learning skills must be mastered within all academic disciplines;
- the applied methods and methods of forming a particular skill should take into account the specifics of this skill, the stages of its development, interdisciplinary ties [172; 85-b.].

The cited requirements were applied to the comprehensive support of the development of general academic skills of the requirements, which carry out long-term educational research and develop projects that include educational-methodological, managerial components. These components that regulate the development of concentrated learning skills (universal educational activities) in students are also considered in the dissertation research work of Educators of our country. For example, it was recommended to include in the explanatory instructions of educational programs of Educational Sciences a list of concentrated learning skills formed on the basis of interdisciplinary connections, as well as methods for their gradual formation.

In the Eighties of the last century, a program for the development of concentrated learning skills and abilities of schoolchildren was presented. The program includes the following in the system of measures that promote the use of the school in the educational process: the implementation of methodological training of teachers, the control and analytical provision of the process and results of teaching concentrated learning skills.

Teachers have also been offered methodological ways of Harakat that reveal the motivational and technological aspects of the formation of cosentrated learning skills, in particular: 1. Awareness of the importance of students ' ability to perform an action. 2. Using the student's ability to perform this action. 3. Using the ability to perform an action to master new skills in a new unfamiliar situation for students [259; 14-b.].

A methodological development on a sequence consisting of the main methods of mental activity that can be applied in solving any problems is presented .

While researchers offer management solutions to their pedagogical communities, its meaning is to develop an intra-school program and prepare a school-wide plan for the formation of common learning skills included in the program, in which the classroom and academic disciplines that provide this formation are also clearly outlined [266; 3-b.].

As a factor affecting the nature of the student's learning - the level of knowledge of the student's learning skills and competencies is indicated [266; P.3.]. At the same time, the authors did not provide methods of diagnosis for assessing the degree of assimilation of concentrated learning skills by schoolchildren.

In the late last century, interest in the problem of concentrated learning skills in pedagogy increased significantly. This is primarily due to the fact that the formation and development of concentrated learning skills within the framework of any educational standards is considered as the main means of increasing the quality limit of any school education.

To use the development of concentrated learning skills in the research activities of schoolchildren in the design of intra-school management technology, we proceed from the following:

- the process of implementing procedures and actions is sufficiently algorithmic, which makes it possible to increase productivity;
- uniformity of implementation of procedures and actions, gives a predictable result;
- an important feature of the technology that contributes to the achievement of management efficiency is the continuity that manifests itself during the transition from order to order, from action to action;
- the advantage of regularity is the optimal integration of personal activity of teachers, the achievement of the set goals is the efforts of methodological associations of teachers and management personnel;
- with this type of interaction, the development of concentrated skills in research activities of schoolchildren becomes a common task of school teachers;
- actions in the personal order can be carried out in Series or in parallel, which in turn brings the management process to a low-cost level;
- periodicity of the procedure the development of general skills concentrated in the research activities of schoolchildren makes it possible to improve the quality of management [244].

Thus, the classification of concentrated learning skills, as well as ensuring the development of concentrated general skills provided by researchers, is important as a factor in managing the development of concentrated learning skills of schoolchildren.

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